
HEALTH SURVEY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN: OUTCOME AND IMPLICATION
FOR STRENGTHENING SCHOOL HEALTH INSPECTION IN ABRAKA, DELTA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Health inspection involves physical observation of the general appearance, mouth and teeth, nose and throat, skin, ears, eyes, scalp and hair, and behavior of children at play. The objective of this study was therefore to conduct a health survey of primary school children with a view to providing relevant information with policy implication for strengthening school health inspection in Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

Method:

This is a school based cross-sectional descriptive study conducted from September 2009 to February 2010 among primary school children in Abraka selected by multistage sampling technique. The study instrument was a pro-forma with twenty items subdivided into two sections.

Results:

The outcome of health inspection of the children revealed that over half (57.1 %) of them had dirty nails, while 45.0 %, 29.8 %, 21.2 %, 18.6 % and 1.8 % of them had dirty uniform, dental caries, skin infections, dirty hair and ear discharge respectively. The association between the occurrence of dirty nails, dirty uniform, dirty hair and dental caries with the type of primary school (private or public) were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), while the association between the occurrence of ear discharge and skin infection with the type of primary school were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$).

Conclusion: This study has revealed the poor state of affairs as regards school health inspection of primary school children in Abraka.

KEYWORDS: Health inspection, outcomes, primary school, children

INTRODUCTION

It is the contention of health professionals, educators and social workers that the provision of school health services is a cost effective way of meeting the health needs of children (Nakajima, 1992). The major health problems of Nigeria school children have been reported to be centred around poor personal hygiene, environmental sanitation, poverty and ignorance (Enahoro and Orok, 1986; Oduntan, 1974). Primary school children are particularly vulnerable to neglect of personal hygiene ([URL:http://www.ifh-homehygiene.org](http://www.ifh-homehygiene.org); [URL:http://www.orc.org](http://www.orc.org)). The consequences in terms of morbidity and mortality are more severe in them compared to adults. Therefore, it would be a welcome development for government to make specific provisions for the rendering of health services in all schools as enunciated in its policy document (Federal Ministry of Education, 1998). School health services refer to the health-care delivery system that is operational within a school or college. The services aim at promoting and maintaining the health of schoolchildren so as to give them a good start in life. In addition, the services seek to enable children benefit optimally from their school learning experiences (Ogbuji, 2003). Health appraisal is a major component of school health services. Health appraisal is that aspect of school health services which concerns itself with evaluating the health of an individual objectively. Health appraisal dovetails into three specific activities, each of which is related to the others. The activities are health inspection (which involves physical observation of the general appearance, mouth and teeth, nose and throat, skin, ears, eyes, scalp and hair, behavior of children at play), health examination (which involves screening tests or medical diagnoses), and health records (which involves the keeping of records of the health histories of the children) (Ogbuji, 2003). Health appraisal is of benefit to school health programme in a number of ways. First, it affords the school authorities the opportunity to detect signs and symptoms of common diseases as well as signs of emotional disturbances that could impede the learning activities of school children.

Besides, health appraisal helps in providing information to parents and school personnel on the health status of school children (Cornacchia *et al*, 1991). However, large scale deficiencies in the provision of school appraisal services have been reported (Cornacchia *et al*, 1991; Nwana, 1988; Nwimo, 2001; Imoge, 1987).

The objective of this study was therefore to conduct a health survey of primary school children with a view to providing relevant information with policy implication for strengthening school health inspection in Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS

This is a school based cross-sectional descriptive study conducted from September 2009 to February 2010 among primary school children in Abraka, a semi-urban town in Ethiope East Local Government Area of Delta State. The study area covers an area of 21.2 square kilometer and is located on longitude 5° 45' N and 6° 15' E of the meridian. It is in the tropical rain forest area of Nigeria and comprises of nine communities namely Otororho, Uhruoka, Ekrejeka, Oria, Ajalomi, Erho, Ugono, Urhovie and Umeghe; with River Ethiope running through. The official language of the people is urhobo and their major occupation is farming.

A minimum sample size of 384 was obtained using the Fischer's formula for population above ten thousand (Araoye, 2003).

$$n = \frac{Z^2 P (1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where n = minimum sample size required

Z= 1.96 (corresponds to 95% confidence level)

P= 50 %

(1-P) = q = 50 %

d = level of precision = 0.05

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 (0.50) (0.50)}{(0.05)^2} = 384$$

Although the computed minimum sample size was 384, a multi-stage sampling technique was however used to select a total of 476 children who gave assent for the study as follows: In the first stage, ten primary schools (five public and five private) were selected from the list of twenty-one primary schools in Abraka by simple random sampling technique. In the second stage, making using the class register, a stratified simple random technique (proportionate sampling) was used to select children from each class level in the ten selected schools. The study instrument was a pro-forma with twenty items subdivided into two sections. Section I recorded the socio-demographic data of the school children such as age, sex, father's educational level, mother's educational level, father's occupation, mother's occupation, family setting and type of school. Section II of the questionnaire elicited information on the status of the hair, nails, skin, mouth and teeth, ears, uniform and general appearance of the pupils.

Data collected was entered into the computer using the SPSS (version 15.0) software. A simple descriptive analysis was carried out to give a general overview of the study population. This was followed by bivariate analysis. The level of significance was set at P< 0.05.

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Health Ethics and Research Committee of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital, Oghara, Delta State. Informed consent was also obtained from the Local Government Education Department, the school authorities and parent-teachers associations of the ten primary schools that were selected.

RESULTS

The socio-demographic characteristics of the children inspected for the study are shown in Table 1. Majority of the children (57.8 %) were in the age group 9-11 years, while 26.3 % and 15.9 % of them were in the age group 6-8 and 12-14 years respectively. Over half of the children were males (52.3 %), live in a monogamous setting (71.8 %) and attend a public primary school (51.3 %).

The outcome of health inspection of the children is shown in Table 2. Over half (57.1 %) of the children had dirty nails, while 45.0 %, 29.8 %, 21.2 %, 18.6 % and 1.8 % of them had dirty uniform, dental caries, skin infections, dirty hair and ear discharge respectively.

The outcome of health inspection in relation to the socio-demographic characteristics of the children is shown in Table 3. The association between the occurrence of dirty nails, dirty uniform, dirty hair and dental caries with the type of primary school (private or public) were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$), while the association between the occurrence of ear discharge and skin infection with the type of primary school were not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$). The association between the occurrence of dirty uniform and ear discharge with age of the children; dirty uniform and dental caries with the sex of the children; dirty uniform and family setting of the children were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

This study has revealed that over half of the children studied had dirty nails, while over and less than a third of them had dirty uniform and dirty hair respectively. This poor state of affairs observed among the children implies a general neglect of health inspection by teachers in primary schools and lends credence to the observations by previous researchers who reported the general absence of school health services in Nigerian schools (Imoge, 1987; Nwana, 1988; Okafor, 1991; Ogbuji, 2003). Health inspection is one of the three specific activities of school health appraisal. It involves the physical observation of the general appearance, mouth and teeth, nose and throat, skin, ears, eyes, scalp and hair, and behavior of school children at play. It is an exercise that involves the teacher's continuous observation and routine morning inspection of school children (Augustine, 2005).

Ordinarily, one would expect that teachers at the primary school level should as a matter of routine observe every facet of the children under their care; but the observation from this study suggests that these teachers do not have the desire, time or training to be involved in the affairs of their school children. This however does not speak well of teachers at the primary school level and should be a matter of concern to all interested parties in children's education. To neglect the health inspection of children amounts to subjecting them to the ravages of preventable diseases. Good health is a necessary condition for learning and there is need for the child's overall health status to be determined regularly through the provision of adequate health appraisal services.

This study also revealed prevalence rates of 29.8 %, 21.2 % and 1.8 % for dental caries, skin infections and ear discharge respectively among the studied children. Although the prevalence of dental caries recorded in this study was lower than the prevalence of 40.0 % recorded by Oduntan, the prevalence of skin infections recorded in this study was however higher than the prevalence of 10.0 % recorded by Oduntan among school children in Ibadan (Oduntan, 1974). This observation further underscores the reason to strengthen school health services in primary schools.

In conclusion, this study has revealed the poor state of affairs as regards school health inspection of primary school children in Abraka. There is need to redress this inadequate state of affairs of school health inspection by teachers. Therefore, it is recommended that the requisite teacher training should be provided or appropriate health care personnel should be hired or employed to ensure regular and adequate health inspection of school children.

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Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the children

Age group (years)	No. Exam.	Frequency	Percent (%)
6-8	476	124	26.3
9-11	476	276	57.8
12-14	476	76	15.9
Sex			
Male	476	255	53.6
Female	476	221	46.4
Family setting			
Monogamous	476	342	71.8
Polygamous	476	134	28.2
Type of school			
Private	476	232	48.7
Public	476	244	51.3

Table 2: Outcome of health inspection conducted among the children

Outcomes	No. Exam.	Frequency	Percent (%)
Dirty hair	476	85	18.6
Dirty nails	476	272	57.1
Dirty uniform	476	214	45.0
Dental caries	476	136	29.8
Ear discharge	476	8	1.8
Skin infections	476	101	21.2
Scabies	476	9	2.0
Skin rash	476	78	17.1
Boil/furuncle	476	8	1.8
Tinea capitis	476	6	1.3

Table 3: Outcome of health inspection in relation to the socio-demographic characteristics of the children

Outcomes	6-8 years	9-11 years	12-14 years	Total	P-value
Dirty hair	19	51	15	85	0.665
Dirty nails	70	161	41	272	0.822
Dirty uniform	38	134	42	214	0.000
Dental caries	34	77	25	136	0.343
Ear discharge	3	4	1	8	0.000
Skin infection	25	56	20	101	0.970
		Male	Female	Total	P-value
Dirty hair		49	35	85	1.980
Dirty nails		146	126	272	0.313
Dirty uniform		129	85	214	0.020
Dental caries		82	54	136	0.028
Ear discharge		4	4	8	0.920
Skin infection		57	44	101	0.515
		Monogamous Family setting	Polygamous Family setting	Total	P-value
Dirty hair		58	27	85	0.470
Dirty nails		186	86	272	0.180
Dirty uniform		137	77	214	0.001
Dental caries		89	47	136	0.090
Ear discharge		5	3	8	0.480
Skin infection					
		Private school	Public school	Total	P-value
Dirty hair		21	64	85	0.000
Dirty nails		93	179	272	0.000
Dirty uniform		65	149	214	0.000
Dental caries		44	92	136	0.000
Ear discharge		2	6	8	0.450
Skin infection		42	59	101	0.750

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